

Title: Comparative Analysis of CRISPR/Cas9 Targeting Efficiency in Three Model Organisms

Abstract:

This paper shall discuss the designing and assessment of CRISPR/Cas9 guide RNAs for directed genome modification in three model organisms of the species *Homo sapiens*, *Mus musculus*, and *Gallus Gallus*. CRISPR, meaning Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats, is a new way to edit organisms' DNA; it has a lot of good features. In this paper, by employing bioinformatic tools like CHOPCHOP, Ensembl, and UCSC Genome Browser, the best candidates for being the most effective gRNAs shall be computationally predicted according to their efficiencies and specificities as gRNAs and to consider functional relatedness. After integrating analyses of conservation and off-target predictions, the proposed work shall offer a methodological framework for in vitro validation with the purpose of better confirming the in-silico predictions and deepening the investigation into the possible biological applications. This indicates that it is greatly significant to make strict strategies to design gRNA according to the genome and the evolution context.

Introduction:

CRISPR-Cas basically revolutionized genome editing; it allowed for very efficient and precise ways of modifying genes. It is the first time in history when manipulation of the genetic material was allowed on that level, accelerating progress in everything from molecular biology to medicine. Critical gRNA design is needed when targeting Cas9 endonuclease to a certain genomic loci in CRISPR editing. High specificity and potency are promised to be provided by efficient gRNA design, basically reducing off-target effects in gene expression within regulatory regions.

Herein, gRNA designs are presented for the following three species: *Homo sapiens*, *Mus musculus*, and *Gallus Gallus*. The three species in this investigation are selected due to their predominance in human health research, biomedical experimentation, and developmental studies Labun et al. (2019). Computational tools, such as CHOPCHOP and the UCSC Genome Browser Kent et al. (2002), have been employed in this research to explore candidate gRNAs within a wide range of genomic and evolutionary contexts. In this study, conservation analysis, functional annotation, and off-target prediction were attached to our gRNA selection to ensure robustness. These will be useful in the design of future experimental validation and point to some challenges and opportunities using CRISPR-mediated genome editing across a wide array of organisms.

Methodology

The analyzed genome, BRCA1, was retrieved from Ensembl. For this study, all of the three species were working with exon 11. Those targeted sequences were ran through the CHOPCHOP gRNA feature to score each gRNA based on efficiency and specificity, but also on genomic target context. Efficiency scores were calculated according to their sequence features, which also includes GC content, presence of a PAM motif, and thermodynamic properties. In addition, sites were rank-ordered, taking into consideration mismatch tolerance and proximity to a regulatory or coding region. Considering the genomic target, the following were in focus: proximity to exons, regulatory sequences, and other regions of interest. In the case of functional genomic context analysis, the genomic loci of the selected gRNAs were analyzed by the UCSC Genome Browser with respect to their overlap with protein-coding exons, introns, and regulatory elements. gRNA also targeted the identification of intronic targets and their eventual impacts on splicing or regulatory functions. Similarly, three off-targets were selected from the gRNA of

highest efficiency and analyzed with regard to whether there is any overlap with an exon or intron. Besides, the conservation analysis was done using 100 Vertebrates Basewise Conservation. Regions of high conservation were selected for their potential functional relevance across species. Regarding the validation of computationally selected gRNAs, the following experimental steps are recommended:

In Vitro Validation: The efficiency and specificity of in vitro Cas9 cleavage assays should be validated.

Off-Target Profiling: Methods like sequencing, such as GUIDE-seq by Tsai et al. 2015, detect unforeseen edits and then quantify them.

In Vivo Validation: Based on the experimental goals, functional studies using an appropriate model system, such as cell lines or whole organisms, need to be implemented in order to understand the phenomenological consequences of the editing and how the editing is interfering with gene expression, protein function, and cellular behavior.

Results:

1. Homo sapiens

gRNA sequence: GGTAAAATGTCCTCTGAGAGG

Efficiency: 61.13%

Off-Targets:

Location B: chr22:39749730 - This site was proximal to an intron, it would probably have a low risk for protein-coding. However, this area needs to be researched more for any possible regulatory elements.

Location C: chr10:31971893 - This site fell within a non-coding region, and thus changes here would probably have little to no biological consequences.

2. Mus musculus

gRNA sequence: TCTGCGAGCAGTCTTCAGAAAGG

Efficiency: 63.28%

Off-Targets:

Target sequence: **TCTGCGAGCAGTCTTCAGAAAGG**

Off-targets		
Location	Number of mismatches	Sequence (including mismatches)
NC_000067.7:53386467	3	TCTGaGAGgAcTCTTCAGAAGGG
NC_000069.7:144136517	3	CCTcTcaGAAGACTGcCcgCAGA
NC_000075.7:91706134	3	CCTTTCTGAAGAcGCTgGCAGg
NC_000076.7:25766807	3	TCTGcTAcCAGaCTTCAGAAAGG
NC_000076.7:80726034	3	TCTGCGAGgAGcCTTCAGgAAGG
NC_000076.7:117171817	3	CCTTTCTGAAGAgTGCgGCAGA
NC_000077.7:35633981	3	TCTGcTAGCAGcCTTCAGAtGGG
NC_000077.7:101413278	0	TCTGCGAGCAGTCTTCAGAAAGG
NC_000081.7:53158506	3	CCTTTCTGAAGAcAGcAtGCAGA
NC_000084.7:78175788	3	CCTTTCTAGgACTGcAgGCAGA

Selection of 3 gRNAs for Off-Target Analysis:

Location A: chr11:101,413,278 - This site fell within a non-coding region, and thus changes here would probably have little to no biological consequences.

Location B: chr9: 91,706,134 - This site fell within a non-coding region, and thus changes here would probably have little to no biological consequences.

Location C: chr10: chr10:117,171,817 - This site also fell within a non-coding region, and thus changes here would probably have little to no biological consequences.

3. Gallus Gallus

gRNA sequence: TTCTCTAATCACATTACTGATGG

Efficiency: 46.92%

Off-Targets:

Target: **fastalInput.fa**

Rank: **1**

Target sequence: **TTCTCTAATCACATTACTGATGG**

Off-targets		
Location	Number of mismatches	Sequence (including mismatches)
chr1:177389296	3	TgCTCTAtTCACATTtCTGATGG
chr1:178547483	3	CCTTCAGTAATGTtTTAGAcAg
chr12:929770	3	CCTTCAGTAATGTcATTAAaAA
chr2:82171677	3	CCTTCAGTAATGTcCTAGAAaAA
chr23:5740697	3	CCTTtAggAATGTGATTcAGAA
chr27:7975441	0	CCATCAGTAATGTATTAGAGAA
chr3:61912897	3	CCTTCAGaAcTGTcTTAGAGAA
chr6:18671222	3	TTCTCtAAtgACATTtCTGAAGG
chr7:11360029	3	CCATCAAtaAATGTGATgAGAGAA

Selection of 3 gRNAs for Off-Target Analysis:

Location A: chr27:7975441 - This site was proximal to an intron, it would probably have a low risk for protein-coding. However, this area needs to be researched more for any possible regulatory elements.

Location B: chr23:5740697 - This site fell within a non-coding region, and thus changes here would probably have little to no biological consequences.

Location C: chr12:929770 - This site fell within a non-coding region, and thus changes here would probably have little to no biological consequences.

Discussion:

The present study shows that along with bioinformatic genome annotation tools, computational predictions can also be used in the design of efficient CRISPR gRNAs. In Homo sapiens, the gRNAs selected herein propose their possible therapeutic applications by targeting exons of genes causing disease, including Breast Cancer, with minimal off-target risks. In Mus musculus and Gallus Gallus, selected gRNAs will enable the study of gene functions in vivo and thus provide helpful tools for model organism research. Conservation analysis indicated that the target sequences falling into the highly conserved regions are more functionally important. For

instance, conserved regulatory regions targeted in *Gallus Gallus* propose the possibility of disrupting developmental pathways which can be experimentally validated using phenotypic assays. On the other hand, intronic targets-for instance, Location A in *Homo Sapiens* are to be considered cautiously for their eventual effects on splicing or regulation of the gene. These results show the variability of efficiency and specificity of gRNAs among species and further put forward the need for better design approaches. While these bioinformatic tools provide the backbone, experimental verification of their correctness and functional relevance still remains a good option. Not targeting any exons by gRNAs reduces the possibility of interference with gene functions or their expressions in manners negative to them. This is advantageous because none of the gRNAs are targeted for exonic regions, hence this could minimize any off-target disruption to protein-coding sequences.

Conclusion:

The present work presents a workflow for designing and thereafter validation of the CRISPR/Cas9 gRNAs, thus providing insights into their applications in multiple species. The present paper hereby combined computational predictions with the analysis of genomic context so as to identify gRNAs that show high performance in a probably therapeutic and experimental setting. Further work will involve experimental verification of the designed gRNAs in order to feedback and refine the computational predictions further for application in various research and therapeutic settings. Advanced techniques such as GUIDE-seq could be incorporated to further improve off-target knowledge and increase precision in CRISPR-based genome editing.

References:

Labun K, Montague TG, Krause M, Torres Cleuren YN, Tjeldnes H, Valen E. (2019).

CHOPCHOP v3: expanding the CRISPR web toolbox beyond genome editing. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 47(W1), W171-W174. doi:10.1093/nar/gkz365.

Kent WJ, Sugnet CW, Furey TS, et al. (2002). The Human Genome Browser at UCSC. *Genome Research*, 12(6), 996-1006. doi:10.1101/gr.229102.

Tsai SQ, Zheng Z, Nguyen NT, et al. (2015). GUIDE-seq enables genome-wide profiling of off-target cleavage by CRISPR-Cas nucleases. *Nature Biotechnology*, 33(2), 187-197. doi:10.1038/nbt.3117.

UCSC Genome Browser: Comprehensive platform for genomic analysis and visualization.

Available at: <https://genome.ucsc.edu/>.

Ensembl Database: Cunningham F, Achuthan P, Akanni W, et al. (2019). Ensembl 2019. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 47(D1), D745-D751. doi:10.1093/nar/gky1113. Available at:

<https://www.ensembl.org/>